

IN-HABIThon

2025

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FEEL

This phase's key points

Understand

What worries you in your environment?
Identifying a focus for action

FEEL

This phase's key points

Keys:

- **Divergence:**
 - not writing down solutions, but pieces of information
 - It is not about agreeing or not, but taking into account different perspectives
- **Convergence:** we search for possible focus for action according to information, not words
- **Synthesis:** we aim for strengthening the group's idea. It is not about the individual post-its notes

FEEL

This phase's key points

- ¿What do you find relevant about the challenge?
 - Write clearly, one sentence per post-it with the relevant information.
- **Organize the information**
 - Based on the content of the post-its, looking for potential areas for action.
- **Identify the action areas**
 - Summarize the content of each cluster into one sentence.
- **Choose a focus**
 - Use a two-round voting process.
- **Deepen your understanding**
 - Summarize what has been learned. Formulate a challenge:
 - How might we... *[increase, reduce, improve, change, optimize, eliminate, create, achieve]* so that... *[users]* can solve the... *[need]* in... *[context]*?

IMAGINE

This phase's key points

IMAGINE

Exploring possibilities

What can we do to change it?

Identifying the plan of action

IMAGINE

This phase's key points

Brainstorming Guidelines:

- Don't judge ideas, neither your own nor others'.
- Quantity matters more than quality.
- The only bad idea is the one that isn't shared.

Keys:

- Make quick and cheap mistakes
- Hands think too

IMAGINE

This phase's key points

- **Generate Lots of Ideas**
 - Without judging, build on others' ideas, and don't be afraid to suggest wild ones.
- **Choose the Best Solutions**
 - Use a two-round voting process.
- **Create a Prototype**
 - Use the materials provided to bring your idea to life.
- **Refine Your Idea**
 - With the help of the template you've been given, clarify your proposal.

DO
Take action

Going from “fiction” to reality

Carry out the action plan

***This time, we will focus on creating an individual action plan, to be filled out using the template provided.**

EVOLUATE
Learning

EVOLVE

Reflect to grow

What have we learned?

Based on the process and thinking
about what could have been

SHARE
One word

SHARE

Tell to inspire

The process is important and it can inspire others*

*Used “IN-HABIThon Communication Guide” to do so.

The process

